

Marketing strategies for building customer loyalty in hotels in João Pessoa-PB

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Abstract

The hotel industry is facing an increasingly competitive market in which customer loyalty is crucial to gaining a competitive edge and increasing profitability. Loyalty programs are valuable strategies for customer retention, especially in an environment of high competition and high acquisition costs. In this context, the general objective of this research was to analyze the loyalty programs used by the hotel sector in João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil. As far as the methodological procedures are concerned, this paper was characterized as descriptive, with a qualitative-quantitative approach, under a field study. Data was collected by applying a questionnaire to 10 hotels located on the beaches of Cabo Branco and Tambaú. The results indicated that, in many cases, there is a growing use of technology and marketing tools to improve customer relations and increase the attractiveness of loyalty programs, especially the use of CRM and e-mail marketing. However, there are significant challenges, such as high costs and a lack of technological integration, which prevent these programs from reaching their full potential. It was suggested that future studies analyze the impact of omnichannel strategies and the use of artificial intelligence in the management of loyalty programs.

Key words: Hospitality, João Pessoa, loyalty, lodging establishments, marketing

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Introduction

The hotel industry has faced significant challenges in an increasingly competitive market, therefore customer loyalty has become a crucial strategy for achieving a competitive advantage and enhancing profitability. In this context, understanding effective marketing tools for fostering customer retention is essential for managers and professionals in the sector.

Among the various strategies for winning over and keeping consumers, loyalty programs stand out. According to Silva (2019), loyalty is an instrument for increasing profitability, as well as strengthening the brand and establishing lasting relationships with the target audience. In the hotel sector,

where competition is fierce and customer acquisition costs are high, strategies are needed to attract and retain customers.

Hotels have been directly impacted by the advance of technology. Platforms such as Airbnb have generated fierce competition between accommodation providers in Brazil. Since renting houses in urban centers has become increasingly common, due to the more competitive prices than hotels (Menezes 2023; Cruz et al. 2024), there has also been a change in the customer profile, which is looking for more personalized experiences and packages.

In this way, loyalty programs play a crucial role in differentiating service offerings, so understanding how loyalty programs are structured and perceived by managers can provide valuable insights for improving local competitiveness in the hotel sector.

Given this scenario, and considering the tourist growth in the capital of Paraíba, along with the development of the hotel industry, which maintained an average occupancy rate of 70% in 2023 (Cardoso 2023), this study addresses the following guiding question: which loyalty programs are used by lodging establishments in the city of João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil? In this context, the general objective of this article was to analyze the loyalty programs used by the hotel sector in João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil.

It is expected this research will contribute to the management practices of local hotels by exploring how loyalty programs can promote continuous growth. Guest loyalty not only strengthens the competitiveness of businesses but also supports regional economic development by encouraging practices that enhance service quality and customer satisfaction. From an academic point of view, investigating these programs provides insights into effective customer relationship management strategies that can be applied across different business contexts.

Theoretical framework

Hotel marketing and customer value

Marketing is a fundamental activity for companies, as it involves the development of strategies to identify, anticipate, and satisfy consumer needs and desires in a profitable manner (Kotler and Armstrong 2007).

Kotler (2000 p. 27) defines marketing as “[...] a social and managerial process by which individuals and groups obtain what they need and want by creating, offering, and exchanging products of value with others”. It is essential to understand that marketing is fundamentally based on the process of exchanges between an organization and its customers.

To ensure these exchanges are effective, maintaining a strong focus on the consumer is imperative. In this sense, Levitt (2004) highlights the importance of understanding customers’ needs and desires rather than focusing exclusively on the services and products offered. Furthermore, with a proactive and anticipatory approach, Drucker (1975 p. 64–65) warned that “[...] the aim of marketing is to make selling superfluous. It is to know and understand the customer so well that the product or service fits and sells itself”.

Grönroos (1994) defines relationship marketing as the process of identifying, establishing, maintaining, enhancing, and, when necessary, ending relation-

ships with customers and other partners profitably, ensuring that the objectives of all parties involved are achieved. This process is achieved through mutual exchanges and the fulfillment of promises, emphasizing the importance of building and maintaining long-term, mutually beneficial relationships. Relationship marketing goes beyond simple transactions, focusing on delivering continuous value for both customers and organizations.

In light of these perspectives, the significance of creating value and building lasting relationships between individuals and organizations becomes evident. Marketing, understood as both an administrative and social process, extends far beyond sales or promotional techniques. It represents a strategic and collaborative effort to satisfy customer needs and desires.

Among various sectors, the hotel industry has increasingly invested in marketing tools to differentiate itself from competitors and foster strong relationships with guests. Castelli (2003, p. 121) states that “[...] hotel marketing is responsible for boosting sales, improving guest service, and publicizing the hotel”. This statement is based on three pillars: first, customer orientation, which consists of focusing on the customer needs rather than those of hotel owners or managers; second, customer satisfaction, which involves meeting and exceeding customer expectations ensuring that all employees prioritize guest needs; and finally, integrated action, which requires the hotel to coordinate the hotel’s internal sectors and employees while fostering collaboration with related companies, partners, suppliers, and tourism agencies aligned with the hotel’s service strategies.

According to Lizis (2010), hotel marketing must be a continuous practice, addressing not only immediate needs but also considering the sector’s sustainability by analyzing market trends to anticipate and satisfy future demands.

The high level of competition in the hotel industry requires hotels to enhance their brand recognition among potential customers to attract more guests. To tackle this challenge, hotels must implement marketing initiatives aimed at boosting brand awareness. Maintaining competitiveness in the hospitality sector demands an effective marketing strategy that strengthens brand visibility and influences potential customers’ purchasing decisions, ultimately leading to higher occupancy rates and a stronger market position (Firdaus and Belgiawan 2023).

In a globalized and highly competitive market, customer retention has emerged as a strategic priority for companies, which also applies to the hotel sector. Increasingly, marketing strategies focus on enhancing the customer experience, as observed through the analysis of social media and websites. Pine and Gilmore (1999) explain that, in today’s economy, the customer experience represents the primary value-add. Creating memorable and engaging experiences for customers is no longer merely a differentiation strategy, but a necessity for businesses aiming to thrive in this economic environment.

Customer loyalty contributes not only to increased profitability but also to brand strength and enduring relationships with the target audience. In this context, loyalty marketing strategies play a crucial role, offering companies tools and approaches to engage, satisfy, and retain customers. As Silva (2019) notes, customer loyalty is fundamental to profitability, as loyal customers generate greater returns over time. Satisfied customers are more likely to maintain their relationship with the organization, resulting in enhanced return on investment for the company.

As Kang et al. (2013) point out customer loyalty is crucial, as explained by Verhoef (2003), in a highly competitive market, customer loyalty serves as the

key driver of business success, so this is the main reason why companies prioritize their relationship with consumers and constantly seek their loyalty.

Given the intense competition in the hotel industry, personalized service has emerged as a critical strategic differentiator. According to Kotler and Keller (2012), personalization enables companies to offer services that meet specific customer needs and expectations. In the hotel context, this involves creating a seamless and individualized guest experience, from booking to check-out, ensuring that each interaction strengthens the relationship between the customer and the brand. Personalization not only enhances customer satisfaction but also strengthens loyalty, encouraging repeat visits and positive word-of-mouth recommendations. In an environment where the customer experience is the primary differentiator, such relationship marketing practices are indispensable.

Turning stays into memorable experiences: the power of loyalty programs

In the hotel industry, the effective management of loyalty programs is essential not only for customer retention but also for establishing a sustainable competitive advantage. According to Reichheld (1996), customer retention is fundamental to a company's economic growth, since loyal customers tend to spend more and exhibit less price sensitivity compared to new customers. The author further highlights the significant financial impact of customer loyalty, as loyal customers often increase their spending over time and are less likely to switch to competitors solely due to lower prices. These aspects are important for understanding the strategic value of loyalty programs in strengthening customer relationships.

According to Chen et al. (2021), loyalty programs are an important marketing instrument used to promote repeat purchases and customer relationships. Thus, loyalty programs aim to encourage and reward customers through a system of rewards for recurring purchases or positive interactions with the brand (Kotler et al. 2017). Maximizing the value of the customer lifecycle is critical for ensuring long-term profitability. Retaining existing customers is generally more cost-effective than acquiring new ones, as loyal customers are more likely to make repeat purchases, increase their spending over time, and recommend the company to others.

Grönroos (2004) points out that satisfied consumers who identify with a brand can act as advocates, engaging in informal promotion and advertising driven by their positive experiences. It means that there is a social benefit to being a consumer that can be understood as a personal recognition from participating in the loyalty program (Gandomil et al. 2013).

Kotler et al. (2017) emphasize the importance of cultivating customer relationships, a valuable aspect that can have a direct impact on an organization's future.

[...] relationship capital is the sum of knowledge, experience, and trust that a company enjoys with its customers, employees, suppliers, and distribution partners. These relationships are generally worth more than the company's physical assets. Relationships determine the future value of the business (Kotler 2003, p. 132).

Leal and Drebes (2014) consider loyalty programs as marketing initiatives that allow customers to accumulate rewards for recurring purchases from the same brand. According to Banasiewicz (2005), loyalty programs are marketing

strategies based on offering incentives, monetary or otherwise, with the main goal of retaining existing customers.

Gómez et al. (2006) outline the range of rewards that loyalty programs can offer, including free products, discounts on goods and services, exclusive promotions for members, invitations to events, and special bonuses at partner companies. According to Leal and Drebes (2014), for a loyalty program to be efficient, companies must have adequate information about their customers to strengthen the relationship with them.

Hotel loyalty programs often allow customers to redeem points for accommodations, similar to how airlines and travel agencies exchange miles. A hotel customer, for example, can benefit from discounts or exclusive promotions by consistently choosing the same establishment.

In addition, other examples of rewards can include exclusive experiences, such as unique offers or events that are only available to members of the loyalty program. Examples of these experiences include access to Very Important Person (VIP) areas, private events, exclusive tours, special tastings, or personalized activities that are unavailable to the general public (Uads 2023).

Strategic partnerships further enhance loyalty programs by collaborating with other businesses or brands to offer additional benefits. A hotel, for example, might partner with local restaurants, spas, retail stores, or tourist attractions to provide discounts or special offers to its loyal guests. Other elements such as gamification, VIP recognition, online communities, and the integration of emerging technologies also play a significant role in modern loyalty programs. These reward tools can be used as main strategies for building customer loyalty (Uads 2023).

According to the Ministry of Tourism, in collaboration with the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), in 2021, lodging represented the largest share of travel expenses. This finding highlights the potential value of loyalty programs that allow customers to accumulate and redeem points for lodging. Such programs offer an appealing resource for the market, enabling customers to earn points based on their reservations and exchange them for benefits such as complimentary stays, and special meals, among other benefits.

The ALL (Accor Live Limitless) program, implemented by the Accor group, is an example of a rewards program that allows participants to earn points by making reservations or using the group's co-working spaces. The program categorizes customers into membership levels (classic, silver, gold, platinum, and diamond), offering a range of benefits such as additional points, discounts on reservations, priority check-in and check-out services, discounts on spas and restaurants, VIP lounge access, among others (Renan 2023).

Other prominent lodging establishments that have adopted points-based loyalty systems include Hilton Honors, Intercontinental Hotel Group (IHG), Marriott Bonvoy, and World of Hyatt.

The Table 1 outlines the benefits of the All-Accor group loyalty program, a free-to-join initiative that offers five membership levels: classic, silver, gold, platinum, and diamond. Each level provides progressively greater rewards and advantages, incentivizing customer engagement and loyalty.

It is important to note that loyalty programs are not limited to major global hotel groups, but they can also be used by inns, apartments, and small hotels such as hostels or motels.

Table 1. Accor group loyalty program. ALL- Accor live limitless.

CLASSIC	SILVER	GOLD	PLATINUM	DIAMOND
Member rate	Welcome drink	Guaranteed room availability	Suite Night upgrade	Free breakfast on weekends
Free Wi-Fi	Priority welcome	Room upgrade	Lounge access	Dining and spa rewards
Exclusive offers	Late check-out	Early check-in or late check-out	Premium Wi-Fi	Free gold status for the person of your choice

Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

Material and methods

This study is characterized as descriptive, with a qualitative-quantitative approach, and conducted as a field study. In the first stage, bibliographical research was carried out on the subjects of marketing, hotel marketing, loyalty strategies and programs, using specialized journals, books, and websites.

The research locus comprised lodging establishments located on the beaches of Cabo Branco and Tambaú, prominent tourist districts in João Pessoa, Paraíba, Brazil. To ensure better focus, the study targeted businesses listed in the Tourism Service Provider Registry (Cadastur). Initially, 30 lodging establishments were identified and invited to participate in the study via e-mail, however, only 10 agreed to collaborate.

Data was collected in September 2024 by means of a questionnaire sent via e-mail to the companies under study. The instrument consisted of 14 questions, 8 of which were closed questions and 6 open questions. It should be noted that there was no interference on the part of the researchers, as the respondents were free to provide and send in their answers. After collecting the data, the closed questions were analyzed quantitatively using Excel, and expressed in graphs. The open questions were discussed using the theoretical framework presented on hotel marketing, loyalty strategies and programs.

Analysis and discussion of the results

Following this framework, the analysis is divided into two parts: the first presents the results of the closed-ended questions using graphs, while the second part shows the results of the open-ended questions.

The questionnaire began by addressing the purpose of loyalty programs, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1 illustrates the questions outlining the general objectives of a loyalty program. The data indicate that increasing revenue is the main objective, accounting for 70% of participants' responses. In the background, customer satisfaction emerges as a significant goal, with 20% of the responses, highlighting the importance of maintaining a positive relationship with consumers. The remaining 10% of responses reflect secondary objectives which, while less prioritized, still contribute to the program's overall effectiveness.

The percentage distribution suggests that, from the perspective of managers, the primary objective of loyalty strategies is revenue maximization. As noted by Silva (2019), although profitability is one of the fundamental premises of loyalty programs, customer satisfaction plays a crucial role in these strategies, as it can directly influence long-term customer loyalty and retention, ultimately driving profitability.

Figure 1. Main objective of loyalty programs. Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

Thus, it is essential for organizations to balance their strategies between revenue generation and the promotion of a positive customer experience to ensure the sustainable success of their loyalty programs. Customer satisfaction can provide valuable insights, guiding the development of strategies that are more aligned with the delivery of personalized and tailored services to the target audience.

In Figure 2, the responses were analyzed to identify the main communication channels used by lodging establishments to promote their loyalty programs. The data reveal that email stands out as the most widely used channel, followed by social media, which emerges as a relevant tool, although to a lesser extent, for promoting these programs. This hierarchy in the use of communication channels suggests that email enables a more personalized and segmented approach, whereas social media provides a platform for broader audience engagement and interaction.

According to Gomes and Mondo (2016), social media can effectively contribute to the dissemination process and the acquisition of new customers for organizations, as these platforms offer broad reach at a low cost. Therefore, if managers integrate their loyalty programs into these platforms, they can expand their reach, making the business more attractive and competitive compared to other enterprises.

Figure 2. Most used communication channels. Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

Social media function as a showcase, fostering interaction, engagement, and relationships among users. Therefore, it is crucial for hotel managers to pay greater attention to optimizing, acquiring, and effectively utilizing these channels in the guest relationship management process.

Figure 3 illustrates the reward strategies targeted at loyal customers. Analysis of the responses reveals that the majority of loyalty strategies focus on exclusive offers, which received five positive responses, indicating a strong preference for benefits that grant privileged access to products or services. In contrast, the options of discounts on future stays and access to special events each received only one positive response, suggesting that although these strategies may hold some value, they are not perceived as being as attractive as exclusive offers.

Figure 4 addresses questions related to the updating of offers by the commercial sector of lodging establishments. The data suggest a relatively limited approach to updating offers, which could affect the effectiveness of loyalty strategies, as the frequency and relevance of offers are crucial factors in maintaining customer engagement.

Figure 3. Reward strategies for loyal customers. Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

Participants were also asked about the use of technological tools in lodging establishments. All respondents confirmed the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, reflecting an awareness of the importance of customer relationship management. CRM systems facilitate the personalization of offers and the segmentation of customer bases, thereby enhancing loyalty strategies.

Regarding the perceived impact of loyalty programs on customer return rates, eight managers reported a moderate impact, while two observed a significant impact. This perception of moderate impact indicates that while loyalty programs are contributing to customer retention, there is room for improvement in their implementation and in communicating the benefits offered. The combined analysis of these data highlight the need for a more dynamic and

Figure 4. Frequency of updating offers. Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

strategic approach to updating offers. Additionally, it highlights the importance of using available technological tools to maximize the potential of loyalty programs and, consequently, to increase customer return rates.

Interviewees' perceptions and experiences with loyalty programs

Regarding question 1, "How does the hotel evaluate the return on its loyalty programs?" some responses present different approaches to evaluating loyalty program effectiveness.

The first response mentions the use of CRM reports and email marketing, indicating a more organized and structured approach to monitoring results. Another response points out the absence of adequate evaluation, highlighting a technological gap that needs to be addressed. An alternative response, on the other hand, offers a broader perspective on the hotel ecosystem, discussing customer segmentation by niches and the gradual return on a brand-strengthening strategy, which showed a notable evolution from 5% to 30% in direct sales between 2022 and 2023.

For question 2, "What are the main difficulties encountered in implementing and maintaining loyalty programs?" some respondents mentioned the difficulty of encouraging customers to make purchases directly through the platform, highlighting the need for continuous and strategic implementation of offers. Some managers point to high costs as a significant barrier, revealing financial constraints. Other responses highlighted the complexity of managing fare plans and the need for continuous adjustment to protect profit margins and commissions for agencies and tour operators, using Revenue Management System(RMS) tools to maintain fare parity.

Two distinct perspectives emerged in response to question 3, "What innovative strategies does the hotel use to increase the attractiveness of its loyalty programs?" One perspective focuses on marketing initiatives, such as using micro-influencers and creative social media posts as the main innovative

strategies, highlighting the role of digital marketing. The second perspective presents a differentiated approach, prioritizing the customer experience over an exclusive focus on pricing, emphasizing strategies that foster a deeper connection between customers and operators.

According to Trivedi et al. (2022), digital influencers are highly effective in hotel marketing, particularly among younger audiences. In today's interconnected world, influencers foster closer engagement with the public, creating desire and generating positive expectations by showcasing products and services.

Both short and long videos have the potential to reach different audiences and generate booking intentions among potential consumers (Trivedi et al. 2022). Therefore, this strategy proves to be valuable from the perspective of promotion, attraction and customer retention.

As for the fourth question, "How does customer feedback influence decisions about rewards and benefits in loyalty programs?" three points were raised by the managers. First, feedback is consistently described as positive and is used to improve actions, such as those related to commemorative dates. The second mentions that customer suggestions are listened to and implemented in future offerings, highlighting the importance of considering customer needs to promote loyalty. Finally, a more strategic perspective focused on adjusting segmentation and refining communication to make rewards more assertive and appealing.

The responses from managers highlight that feedback is a key element in the evaluation process of implemented programs. This is a relevant finding, as it indicates that entrepreneurs are attentive and receptive to customer input. When effectively managed, this openness enables the development of internal indicators for continuous improvement, enhancing the quality of loyalty programs.

In response to question number 5, "How do strategic partnerships with other companies affect loyalty programs?" two key perspectives emerged. The first considers partnerships as relative, depending on each hotel's strategy. The second response provides a more nuanced analysis, criticizing the reliance on Online Travel Agencies (OTAs), which promote their own brands rather than the hotel's, leading to controlled distribution strategies aimed at avoiding outsourcing that lacks alignment with the hotel's identity.

Finally, question 6, "How is emerging technology transforming loyalty programs in hotels?" received the most consistent responses. The majority viewed technological advancements positively, emphasizing that new trends add value to the market. However, it was also highlighted that most hotels in the city still do not use loyalty programs, pointing to a technological lag.

Another critical point raised was the exponential growth in data generation and the challenge of filtering it to produce practical insights, underscoring the crucial role of technology in the evolution of loyalty programs.

Figure 5 presents a word cloud derived from the interviews, based on the theoretical foundations emphasizing the importance of certain themes for customer loyalty and the implementation of these processes within the João Pessoa hotel sector. This figure highlights the most frequently mentioned terms related to loyalty programs, with marketing, CRM, RMS, offers and investment being the most important.

Figure 5. Highlighted words. Source: Elaborated by the authors (2024).

Conclusion

The results indicate a growing reliance on technology and marketing tools to enhance customer relationships and increase the attractiveness of loyalty programs. However, the study also highlights significant challenges, such as the high costs and lack of technological integration that prevent these programs from reaching their full potential.

A positive point that emerges from the research is the awareness of the importance of personalizing offers and effective customer communication. Many respondents highlight the use of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems to segment audiences and customize rewards, showcasing progress in strategic customer relationship management. Additionally, customer feedback emerges as a key factor for ongoing refinements to rewards and benefits, reflecting efforts to align programs with consumer expectations.

The study also demonstrated that email marketing is one of the primary tools for customer communication, reflecting an effective strategy for personalization and outreach. However, the limited use of other platforms, such as social media, suggests an opportunity for a more comprehensive and diversified approach that combines different communication channels to maximize customer engagement.

On the other hand, the challenges faced in implementing and maintaining loyalty programs are significant. High costs are among the main barriers

mentioned, hindering the expansion of programs or the adoption of more advanced technologies. Furthermore, some responses indicate that many hotels are still in the early stages of developing their loyalty programs, without clear or sophisticated strategies. This reflects a significant gap between hotels that have already embraced a more technological and innovative approach and those still struggling with basic difficulties.

Regarding the impact of loyalty programs on customer return rates, many managers perceive the effect to be moderate. This suggests that, although these programs contribute to customer retention, significant untapped potential remains. Loyalty programs appear underused in optimizing customer returns, potentially due to irregular updates to offerings and limited use of data for personalization.

Based on the analyses, several relevant themes for future research can be identified. The first theme would be the impact of omnichannel strategies on loyalty programs, exploring how the combination of different communication channels (email, social media, apps) can enhance customer engagement. Furthermore, the personalization of offers based on data collected through CRM and other technological tools could be investigated further, focusing on how this approach influences customer retention and the perceived value of loyalty programs.

Another interesting theme for future studies would be the application of artificial intelligence and automation in managing these programs. The use of machine learning to predict customer behavior and automatically adjust offers would represent an innovation that could lead to more significant outcomes. Additionally, it would be important to explore how strategic partnerships between hotels and companies from other sectors, such as airlines and ride-sharing apps, can add value to loyalty programs and increase customer satisfaction.

Finally, a more in-depth study on the fragmentation of the hotel market and the influence of OTAs (Online Travel Agencies) on the direct relationship between hotels and their customers could offer valuable insights on how to recover this connection through loyalty programs. These themes are highly relevant, considering the current context of the hospitality sector, where technology and customer experience play central roles in building loyalty.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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